

Quantification of Heavy Metals In Cassava In Adikpo Township And Agbaikyan Council Ward In Kwande Local Government Area of Benue State

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Abstract: The expediency of food safety and security globally informed this research direction, determining the concentration of heavy metals in cassava in two selected council wards in Kwande Local Government Area of Benue State-Nigeria. A total of twenty (20) samples were collected from the two council wards, four (4) samples from the major settlements and four (4) from the minor settlements within the two wards of the local government. The samples were analyzed for heavy metals concentration using Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) at the Department of Chemistry, Benue State University Makurdi. Zinc (Zn), Lead and Manganese (Mn) had escalated value above the standard recommended by WHO, USEPA and NSFQ. Copper (Cu) and Cadmium (Cd) have values declined within and below acceptable limit of WHO, USEPA and NSFQ.

Keywords: Quantification of Heavy Metals, Agbaikyan Council

INTRODUCTION

We defined radiation as the energy emitted in form of waves or streams of particles either transmitted or absorbed by matter [1]. The level of radiation in soil, sand and rocks depend on the local geology of each region in the world. Naturally occurring radioactive materials generally contain terrestrial origin radionuclide's left over since the creation of the earth. In addition, the existence of some springs, quarries and building material emits background radiation which may raise the dose rate of background radiation in an ecosystem [2].

Soil is one of the fundamental sustenance of food crops, regardless of the type and it can be greatly perturbed by heavy metals present from the point sources (e.g., energy-intensive industries, such as agricultural activities, thermal power plants and coal mines, and chlor-alkali chemical industries, such as goldmines, smelting, electroplating, textiles, leather, and e-waste processing) and non-point sources (e.g., soil/sediment erosion, agricultural runoff, and open freight storage). Research indicated that, in addition to their human health implications, heavy metals adversely affect soil biota through microbial processes and soil-microbe interactions [3]. Beneficial soil insects (especially in agriculture), invertebrates, and small and large mammals are all affected in no small measure [4].

Studies showed there are over 50 elements that can be classified as heavy metals, 17 of which are considered to be very toxic and relatively accessible. Toxicity level depends on the type of metal; its biological role and the type of organisms that are exposed to it. With no doubt, heavy metals have a marked effect on the aquatic flora and fauna which through biomagnifications enters the food chain and ultimately affect the human beings as well for it is a chain transmission [5].

Some of these metals include, copper (Cu), chromium (Cr), fluorine (F), molybdenum (Mo), nickel (Ni), selenium (Se) or zinc (Zn), arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg) and lead (Pb) etc [6]. Among the heavy metals As, Cd, Pb, Cr, Cu, Hg and Ni are of major concern, mainly due to their presence at relatively high concentrations in food substances and their effects on human health. Among the heavy metals, As, Cd and Pb have extensively been studied for their public health effects by researchers and even more investigations are on in the world of science [7].

The high level of environmental contamination by these metals is dangerous owing to their uptake by plants and subsequent transmission and accumulation in food crops consumed by humans and animals is deleterious to health. There are many known avoidable and unavoidable sources of harmful metals, including the earth, which releases them into

food, air, water, and anthropogenic activities, such as the application of fertilizer in agriculture, the use of pesticides and herbicides, and irrigation activities. Other sources could be automobile emissions, paints, cigarette smoking, industries, and sewage and waste disposal [8].

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Twenty (20) samples of cassava were collected, ten (10) from each of the council wards, two (2) samples from the eastern, northern, western, northern and central part and taken to Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Benue State University (BSU) Makurdi. The collected samples were washed with distilled water to remove dirt, peeled to remove their coats, sliced into smaller size using a stainless steel knife and dried for seven days. The dried samples were grounded into powdered form using mortar and pestle at the laboratory. A 2g weight of the sample was placed in a 50ml beaker. 20ml of concentrated Nitric acid was added to the sample, vigorously shaken for a proper mixture. The beaker was swirled gently, heated on an electric heating plate placed in a film held at a temperature of 120°C till a clear solution was obtained. For all the organic matter to digest properly, a drop of concentrated nitric acid was added. The digested samples were left to cool for about thirty minutes and then filtered through whatman No. 42 filter paper. The resulting solution was transferred into 50ml graduated flask and made up to the mark with purified water. The prepared (digested) samples were then quantified with the help of Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result from this current study showed that among the heavy metals, Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu), Manganese (Mn), Lead (Pb) and Cadmium were detected from the samples. The table below shows the concentration of each heavy metal in their respective sample locations.

Table 1: Samples with their concentration in mg/l

SAMPLE ID	Zn(mg/l)	Cu(mg/l)	Mn(mg/l)	Pb(mg/l)	Cd(mg/l)
AD1	1.486	0.237	0.739	0.097	0.064
AD2	0.972	0.102	0.671	0.054	0.069
AD3	0.338	0.133	0.588	0.119	0.086
AD4	0.284	0.231	0.522	0.187	0.096
AD5	0.248	0.250	0.558	0.193	0.072
AD6	1.254	0.087	0.540	0.122	0.071
AD7	1.004	0.227	0.610	0.091	0.080
AD8	0.145	0.204	0.511	0.120	0.064
AD9	1.410	0.172	0.560	0.174	0.077
AD10	1.220	0.130	0.355	0.092	0.081
AG1	0.974	0.220	0.357	0.181	0.087
AG2	1.116	0.021	0.406	0.042	0.063
AG3	1.361	0.009	0.333	0.131	0.056
AG4	0.992	0.155	0.300	0.144	0.060
AG5	1.033	0.132	0.343	0.188	0.069
AG6	1.255	0.204	0.425	0.128	0.071
AG7	1.311	0.211	0.400	0.119	0.061
AG8	1.343	0.193	0.372	0.109	0.069
AG9	1.292	0.181	0.377	0.110	0.059
AG10	1.333	0.150	0.409	0.065	0.055

Figure 1: Samples and their concentration in mg/l

DISCUSSION

They are about fifty heavy metals, of which twenty are considered been toxic and radioactive, five among these were identified from the analysis. Table 1 above showed the actual concentration of heavy metals in the sample. In-depth look on the table showed that Zinc ranged from 0.145 to 1.486 mg/l with average of 0.816 mg/l all the values were higher than the reference value by NSFQ (0.003 mg/l), WHO (0.003 mg/l) and USEPA (0.005mg/l). Agricultural practices such as application of inorganic manure such as fertilizers and the use of fungicides could be responsible for the high value just as leaching from the soil may not be out of the cause [9].

Also, Copper had its value from 0.009 to 0.250 mg/l with an average of 0.130 mg/l. All the values were lower than the recommended value set by NSFQ (1mg/l) and (2mg/l) by WHO. In a similar way, Manganese ranges from 0.300 to 0.739 mg/l with an average of 0.520 mg/l. All the values were higher than the standard set by WHO (0.4 mg/l), USEPA (0.005mg/l) and NSFQ (0.2 mg/l) except in AD10, AG1, AG3, AG4 and AG5. Mn and Cu increased concentration could be attributed to the use of phosphate fertilizers, detergents, used batteries, refined products and other chemicals like fungicides [10].

Lead had values higher than the reference by WHO (0.01 mg/l) and NSFQ (0.01 mg/l) in all the samples. Cadmium in all the samples was below the safe international limit of 1mg/l by WHO. Researches revealed how various effects are associated with heavy metals contamination on human food and water (Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry [6]. International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) after a study reported that inorganic Arsenic (As) and Cadmium (Cd) are classified as human carcinogens especially on accumulation via food contaminations [11]. Associated with cancer risk and skin damage, Cadmium (Cd) is akin to kidney damage and cancer. Both stochastic and deterministic effects such as heart diseases and blood cholesterol from Sb, Anemia from Pb, kidney and liver damage from Hg, and gastrointestinal disorder from Cu were also made known in several reports [6].

CONCLUSION

Comparing the outcome of this work with WHO, USNRC, USEPA and NSFQ acceptable standard concentration of heavy metals in food crops, it can be concluded that the concentration varied from metal to metal with different trend which largely fall below the established maximum limits. Attention should be drawn to the prevailing rise in the Zinc, Lead and Manganese. This largely may be attributed to chemical toxic contaminants from pesticides, herbicides and inorganic manures during agricultural practices. In order to substantiate these findings, observation and supplement existing information, further investigation is required in other council wards and for other food crops. For numerous factors could subsequently lead to a decline in the concentration of those heavy metals in those locations. Seeing that a

vast percentage of farmers in the locality are ignorant of the implications of some agricultural practices, it is crucial that necessary Federal and State Agencies, private organizations and even international agencies partner, disseminate useful agricultural innovations and research results to ensure food security in the country and for export purposes.

LIMITATION

With no iota of doubt, limitations could exist at one stage or the other of this research, from the point of sample collection, preparation, apparatus used and preparation, digestion of the samples, collection of data, analysis of the data and the methods used, interpretations and representation. None has obvious source of error owing to avoidable limitations, however, exclusive efficiency of 100% isn't guarantee, unforeseen could constitute limitations to the optimal and overall research performance.

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